

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Presentations and Teaching

Use Case

Alex Hüsler is working on a dissertation about the influence of group behavior on young adults between the ages of twenty and twenty-five. The dissertation uses social-psychological experiments that are recorded on video.

Alex Hüsler obtains informed consent from all the participants to collect and analyze the data in the context of his dissertation and assures them that the data will only be used in an anonymized form in publications.

Alex Hüsler now has the opportunity to present the initial results at a conference. To make the presentation more engaging, Alex Hüsler would like to illustrate the results with short video sequences. In addition, Alex Hüsler has been asked to design a series of seminars for master's students. In the seminar series, Alex Hüsler wants to go into detail about the methods used in the dissertation and would like to use the collected video material to do so, but consent was not obtained for these specific areas of application from the study subjects. Alex Hüsler assumes that this is not a problem, since the data will only be shown to a very limited group of colleagues or students on both occasions and will not be disseminated.

Is it allowed to use personal data for presentations and teaching?

May the data or parts of the data be presented at conferences?

Alex Hüsler is not allowed to present the data in a non-anonymized form at a conference without first obtaining [informed consent](#) to do so. The length of the video sequences, the limited number of conference participants, and the fact that the data will only be presented and not disseminated are not relevant. By contrast, Alex Hüsler is allowed to process, present, and publish anonymized data without having to obtain consent. So if Alex Hüsler is able to anonymize the data, the sequences may be shown at the conference. If anonymization is not possible, Alex Hüsler can still try to obtain consent from the individuals concerned to present the data in a non-anonymized form.

May the data or parts of the data be used for teaching?

The above also applies to using the data for teaching. Even if the data are only made available to a limited audience, explicit permission must be obtained from the study participants. If Alex Hüsler does not have such permission, then it is only possible to use anonymized videos. One should keep in mind that anonymizing videos completely requires a lot of effort, and depending on the situation, it may be almost impossible. But in this case too, it is possible to obtain consent retrospectively.

Generally speaking, it does not make a difference whether non-anonymized data appear in a publication, are made available on a repository, or are used for

teaching or at conferences. In each of these cases, the consent of the study participants is required.

What does that mean for this case?

Since the videos for the conference presentation are only short sequences that can be anonymized without great technical difficulty or a large time investment, Alex Hüsler decides to include them in an anonymized form.

Using the videos for the seminar series is more difficult. Even with a great deal of technical difficulty and a huge time investment, it would not be possible to anonymize the videos in such a way that they could be reused in a meaningful manner. Alex Hüsler therefore decides to obtain subsequent consent from the study participants to use the videos for teaching. Unfortunately, none of the participants are willing to make the data available. Alex Hüsler must therefore rely only on the anonymized data for the seminar series. Fortunately, during research at the beginning of the project, Alex Hüsler found a study that had experiments with a similar methodology and whose data are freely available. For the seminar, Alex Hüsler uses these freely accessible videos in addition to the anonymized findings.